

FOSS4G

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Academic Track Proceedings

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Preface

FOSS4G is the acronym for Free and Open Source Software for Geospatial. It is the annual recurring global event hosted by OSGeo, the non-profit organization that supports and promotes the collaborative development of free and open source geographic technologies and open geospatial data. The academic track of FOSS4G 2024 showcases the dynamic interaction between academia and the wider open-source geospatial community, highlighting the fundamental role of free and open-source geospatial software in addressing contemporary challenges. This edition follows in the footsteps of the emblematic FOSS4G 2021 Buenos Aires, held online during the COVID-19 pandemic. A milestone in fostering collaboration across regions and disciplines, the conference will be held for the first time in person in Latin America, in Belém, Brazil, from December 2 to 8, 2024.

This volume of Proceedings comprises the papers presented at the Academic Track of FOSS4G 2024. The Program Committee accepted 25 papers, that were included in the program in 16 oral presentations and 9 poster presentations. Accepted papers covered topics such as machine learning for geospatial analysis, community-driven geospatial solutions, and innovative uses of OpenStreetMap in local and global contexts. Emerging themes emphasise the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and geospatial technologies, as seen in studies using natural language processing, semantic association tools, and advanced photogrammetry methods. These papers highlight the transformative potential of open-source geospatial solutions in fields ranging from environmental conservation to urban planning and public health. The symbiotic relationship between open-source geospatial technologies and academic research is at the heart of this year's discussions. Projects such as GeoNode, WebODM for photogrammetry, and Earth Observation Datacubes demonstrate how collaborative frameworks drive innovation while adhering to open standards and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. Integrating academic rigour with community-driven development fosters solutions that are not only technologically robust but also socially impactful.

This collection of papers highlights the importance of FOSS4G as a catalyst for knowledge sharing and the democratisation of geospatial data and technologies. It underscores the ongoing commitment of the open-source geospatial community to build inclusive, accessible and sustainable geospatial infrastructures that address critical global challenges.

We express our gratitude to all members of the Program Committee whose efforts were crucial in ensuring the quality of each accepted paper. Special thanks are extended to the local organization of FOSS4G 2024 for their dedicated support in the preparation and execution of the conference. Finally, our appreciation goes to the supporters of FOSS4G 2024.

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